

Rat brain preparation for *ex-vivo* MRI protocol

By:

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Autolysis, a process of self-degeneration, is initiated after death by the tissues' own autogenous enzymes. Therefore, for *ex-vivo* MRI tissue must be preserved in a way to stop autolysis as well as microbial formation and tissue degradation (i.e., breakdown of cellular membranes).

Chemical fixation with 4% formaldehyde intracardiac perfusion preserves the microstructural characteristic of tissue.

Experimental protocol and the use of animals must be approved by the ethical committee.

Protocol:

1. Materials

- Chemical fume hood,
- Anesthesia system (isoflurane) + analgesic (subcutaneous injection of Buprenorphine (Temgesic, ESSEX) 0.03mg/ml at a dosage of 1 μ L/gr) or injectable anesthesia with analgesic effect (ketamine (75 mg/kg) and xylazine (5 mg/kg)),
- PBS 1x,
- Fresh 4% formaldehyde solution in PBS – 150 mL per animal,
- Laboratory peristaltic pump,
- Perfusion tubing (three tubes connected with Luer Lock Adapter 3 Way Stopcock T-Connector)
- 19-G needle
- 1-ml syringe
- Blunt scissors
- Micro dissection scissors

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- Guillotine
- Bone rongeurs
- 50 mL Falcon tube
- Glass beaker
- Ice bucket
- Tweezers
- Hemostat
- White light system
- Galden R HT270 (Apollo Scientific Ltd)
- Syringes for brain fixation (adapt volume to the brain size) – for MRI
- Rubber septum
- Desiccator
- Vacuum pump system (eg. KNF Vacuum Pump System SC 920 G)

2. Perfusion pump set up

- 2.1 This perfusion needs to be performed in a fume hood since formaldehyde is hazardous.
- 2.2 Assemble all tools necessary for the perfusion surgery (fig. 1)
- 2.3 Place one of the inflow tubing of the pump into the PBS 1x and fill the tube,
- 2.4 Switch the stopcock valve and fill the tube with 4% formaldehyde,
- 2.5 Switch the stopcock valve again to the PBS 1x and flush the tubing from eventual residues of formaldehyde,
- 2.6 Keep the tube filled with PBS 1x,
- 2.7 Dislodge any air bubbles that form along the lines,
- 2.8 Adjust the pump settings so that the flow rate is 11-12 ml per minute.

Fig. 1. Peristaltic pump with the perfusion setup.

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3. Perfusion surgery

- 3.1 Put the animal under anesthesia by induction (~4min) with isoflurane 4% with oxygen 50% and air flow of 0,5 L/min,
- 3.2 After induction place the animal dorsal on a 37 °C heating pad, insert the rat nose in the anesthesia mask,
- 3.3 Maintain anesthesia of the rat by inhalation of 1.5-3 vol% isoflurane in 50% oxygen at a flow rate of 0.5 L/min and induce analgesia by subcutaneous injection of Buprenorphine (Temgesic, ESSEX) 0.03mg/ml at a dosage of 1µL/gr
- 3.4 Wait 15 min for the analgesic effect of Buprenorphine,
- 3.5 Shave the abdominal fur of the rat with an electric fur shaver,
- 3.6 Pinch the paw to test for absence of paw retraction and ensure that the rat has reached a surgical plane of anesthesia/analgesia prior to starting the perfusion surgery,
- 3.7 Using a hemostat or tweezers, lift the skin over the ribs. Then, using blunt scissors, cut 1 cm into the abdominal wall beneath the rib cage,
- 3.8 Pay attention to not cut the liver when inserting the blunt side of the scissors into the abdominal opening and carefully cut up to the sides of the ribs,
- 3.9 Using the hemostat or tweezers, grasp the exposed sternum and cut the connective tissue that joins the liver to the sternum,
- 3.10 To access to the pleural cavity, make a little incision in the diaphragm, cautiously insert the blunt end of the scissors, and keep cutting all the way through,
- 3.11 Cut down both sides of the rib cage up to the collarbone using blunt scissors. Take care not to cut the lungs.
- 3.12 Carefully cut the tissue that joins the heart to the ribs by lifting up the sternum. Make sure you can see whole heart and have free access to the ventricles and atria and the inferior vena cava,
- 3.13 Insert the 19 G needle connected to the perfusion system into the left ventricle Fig. 2 and Fig. 3A,
- 3.14 Cut the right atrium or the inferior vena cava for the blood to leak freely Fig. 2 and Fig. 3A,
- 3.15 Turn on the pump and perfuse first with PBS x1 for 1min to flush out the blood,
- 3.16 At this point you can stop the isoflurane anesthesia,
- 3.17 Then, turn the valve and launch the perfusion with the fixative for 10 min. Within a few seconds, fixation tremors should be noticed.
- 3.18 The fluid must be flowing freely. A proper perfusion is indicated by the liver Fig. 3A or eyes clearing Fig. 3B,
- 3.19 As soon as the perfusion is finished, cut the rat's head off with a guillotine.

Formaldehyde that has been used needs to be collected and preserved in accordance with your institution's rules before being disposed as a chemical waste at unit designated for this purpose.

Fig. 2. Surgical exposure of the rat's heart, right ventricle, abdominal aorta and inferior vena cava.

Fig. 3. (A) Perfusion - needle placed into the left ventricle. **(B)** Eyes clearing.

4. Brain removal

- 4.1 To reveal the skull, make a midline incision from the neck to the nose along the integument.
- 4.2 Make sure to use scissor or rongeurs to remove any leftover neck muscle so the skull is well exposed,
- 4.3 Remove the skull overlying the brain using bone rongeurs,
- 4.4 Cut the dura, nerves, and connective tissue carefully with iris scissors,
- 4.5 Tease the brain gently away from the cranium Fig. 4,
- 4.6 Place the brain in a 50 mL falcon tube filled with 4% formaldehyde.

Fig. 4. Extracted brain

This protocol can be also applied to other organs as well as to a whole head. For the whole head specimen, the skin must be removed.

Fig. 5. Whole rat head specimen

5. Post-fixation & Storage

- 5.1 Keep the brain in fixative and store at 4°C for 24 hours,
- 5.2 Wash the brain three times with phosphate-buffered saline after 24 hours by changing the medium every 10 minutes,
- 5.3 Transfer the brain into PBS containing 0.01% sodium azide (NaN_3) for long term storage at 4°C.
Overfixation with formaldehyde will create changes in tissue properties and compromise quantitative MRI measurements.
- 5.4 **Fixation and cleaning intervals should always be the same for each sample for comparable measurements.**

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6. Brain embedding in Galden for MRI

- 6.1 Prepare the syringe by removing the piston and cut its end Fig. 6A,
- 6.2 Slide in the brain on the brain holder Fig. 6B,
- 6.3 Fill the syringe with Galden and close well the end with a rubber septum Fig. 6C,
- 6.4 Branch via luer with another syringe (exchange unit) for gas – liquid exchange while degassing Fig. 6C,
- 6.5 Place the setup (brain in the syringe) into the desiccator, set the pressure to 40 mbar and launch the pumping Fig. 6D,
- 6.6 Pump the sample ~30 min. The air bubbles will be released and will be visible at the exchange unit (the syringe on top) Fig. 6E,
- 6.7 After 30 min. stop pumping, open the valves and reach the ambient pressure.
- 6.8 Test if there are no more air bubbles by launching the pump again and wait till the pressure will reach a 100 mbar, if no bubbles stop pumping and open the valves,
- 6.9 As you reach the ambient pressure take the setup out of the desiccator,
- 6.10 Withdraw the excess of Galden with Pasteur pipet but leave a small amount on the bottom of exchange unit to create a meniscus Fig. 6F & G,
- 6.11 Remove the exchange unit and close the setup with luer cap. Clean the excess of Galden that will flows out while closing Fig. 6H.
- 6.12 Your sample is ready for MRI.

7. Brain retrieval after MRI for histological assessments

- 7.1 Open the luer cap and place the setup over the liquid trash container. Remove the rubber septum and empty the setup.
- 7.2 Empty the Galden into the bottle with used Galden **for further disposal as a chemical waste at unit designated for this purpose.**
- 7.3 Move the brain into the beaker with PBS and wash it at least three times for 10 min to remove the Galden. Stir from time to time the beaker to improve the cleaning procedure.
- 7.4 Transfer the brain into PBS containing 0.01% sodium azide (NaN_3) for long term storage at 4°C.

Fig. 6. Setting the brain for MRI. (A) MRI setup – brain holder. **(B)** Brain placed on the brain holder. **(C)** MRI setup with brain fixed with the exchange unit. **(D)** MRI setup placed into the desiccator for degassing. **(E)** Presence of air bubbles at the exchange unit during degassing. **(F)** Removing of the Golden excess with Pasteur pipet. **(G)** The exchange unit is removed and the Golden meniscus is visible. **(H)** MRI setup closed with luer cap.